

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Том 1, Выпуск 4, 30 Декабря
DIABETES DURING PREGNANCY

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Abstract. Diabetes in pregnant women (gestational diabetes) was detected during pregnancy. But definite (newly diagnosed) diabetes is a disease characterized by hyperglycemia that does not meet the criteria for diabetes. A history of gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) has been identified by many diabetes specialists as predisposing women to type 2 diabetes (NIDDM). It has been studied that diabetes can occur even after childbirth.

Абстрактный. Сахарный диабет у беременных (гестационный диабет) выявлен во время беременности. Но определенный (вновь диагностированный) диабет – это заболевание, характеризующееся гипергликемией, не отвечающее критериям диабета. Многие специалисты по диабету определили, что гестационный сахарный диабет (ГСД) в анамнезе предрасполагает женщин к диабету 2 типа (НИСД). Было изучено, что диабет может возникнуть даже после родов.

Key words: Pregnancy. Diabetes. Hyperglycemia. Anamnesis. Prediabetes. Illness. Pathology

A new person is formed in the body of a pregnant woman. This is a very responsible and complex process. This period lasts 9 months. During these 9 months, various processes take place in a woman's body. A woman prepares to bear a child and become a mother. In this complex process, the processes in the body of a woman suffering from diabetes become more complicated. Therefore, a pregnant woman living with diabetes should know and learn about diabetes during pregnancy (gestational diabetes), its specific aspects. Only then will he focus on himself and his health. The first of pregnancy Eight weeks is the most important period of fetal development.

In addition, it is important for a woman to pay special attention to her physiological and mental state at every stage of pregnancy. Usually pregnancy lasts 40 weeks or 9 months. The period of pregnancy is the gestational period

is called Every three months is called a trimester. The first trimester is the first trimester, the second trimester is the second trimester, and the last trimester is the third trimester.

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First trimester. In the first three months of pregnancy, the main of the fetus body organs (heart - it begins to circulate blood, digestive system, spine) and systems are formed. The placenta begins to develop as a member of protection and nutrition, and performs the function of a filter, providing the fetus with necessary nutrients, and becoming a barrier to unnecessary ones. In the eighth week, the fetus begins to develop eyes (only while it is still closed), lips, tongue, hands (elbows, wrists), legs (knees, ankles). A child born before the ninth week is called an embryo, and then a fetus. At the end of the first trimester, the length of the fetus is 7.5 cm, and its weight is 29.0 grams. Kidney, tooth position, claws on paws in general, main organs and

systems are formed. Bones and muscles also develop. Hair on the head and eyelashes begin to grow. During these periods, fatigue is often felt in the mother's body.

Second trimester. During this period, the growth and development of the fetus continues, its weight can be 200.01 grams, height 17.0-18.0 cm. The heartbeat of the fetus will be more noticeable, and the doctor will be able to hear it with a stethoscope. At this time, pregnancy hormones start to work. A pregnant woman's breasts may become enlarged and painful.

The skin around its tip becomes dark. The uterus grows and squeezes the bladder. Therefore, urination is accelerated. The nipples may become red and bleed.

Therefore, it is necessary to keep the oral cavity and teeth clean. At the end of the second trimester (6 months), the weight of the fetus increases to 715 grams and the height increases to 27.5-35 cm.

Fetal eyelids open, eyelashes grow, nails grow to the end of the fingers. In general, vital systems of the fetus develop and improve, and the woman's belly becomes visible. As the fetus grows, its height also changes. Stomach upset, heartburn can be annoying.

Third trimester. All vital organs and systems of the fetus can be formed. The skull is soft and pliable. Growth will accelerate. At the end of the seventh month, the weight of the fetus will be 1022-1227 grams, and its height will be 35-42.5 cm. During this trimester, the child is ready for birth, its weight is 2965-3067.54 grams, and its height is 50 cm. In each period, the fetus prepares for external life in the womb. In order to have an idea about the changes specific to each trimester, every pregnant woman should have information about the trimester.

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